

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Humanoid Attitudes Influence Humans in Video and Live Interactions

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ABSTRACT During social interactions, actions can be performed with different forms as a function of the mood driving them. These action forms i.e. vitality forms (VFs), have a strong influence in human interactions allowing people to immediately understand the attitude of others. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that the gentle and rude VFs expressed by a human agent influence the motor behavior of the receiver. An intriguing issue to investigate was to assess whether and how a humanoid agent, able to generate VFs, may induce the same contagion effect on the human partner. To this purpose we carried out a kinematic experiment investigating the motor behavior of participants in response to actions (taking request) performed by the iCub robot with different VFs in video and live interactive contexts. During the experiment, participants were required to pay attention to the iCub robot request and subsequently to place a ball on a specific target. Results indicate that: a) vitality forms conveyed by the iCub robot influenced the motor response of participants, modulating some kinematic parameters; b) this effect was obtained for both video and live interactive contexts; c) this effect was significantly greater in the video session compared to the live one.

INDEX TERMS Action forms, humanoid robots, human-robot interaction, social science.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human interactions depend on the mutual exchange of actions and speech, involving explicit and implicit signals like body posture, gaze direction, and voice tone. The encoding of these signals enhances the quality of the interaction by revealing the partners' intentions, necessities, desires and even their positive/negative attitudes. Indeed, a peculiar human feature regards the possibility to modulate motor behavior according to the health state, social context and feelings. For example, a vigorous handshake may reveal friendliness, sociability or dominance, whereas a delicate handshake may reveal shyness, gentleness or sickness. These forms characterizing

human communication were defined vitality forms (VFs) by Stern [1], [2]. Previous studies showed that when interacting with others, the gentle or rude VFs expressed by a human agent through action or voice influence the motor behavior of a human receiver [3], [4]. In particular, when participants perceived a rude request their subsequent motor response was characterized by a higher velocity and covered a longer distance, while when they perceived a gentle request they produced a soft response, corresponding to a lower velocity and a shorter distance. These data clearly indicate that, during interpersonal human-human interactions, VFs expressed by an agent affect the motor behavior of the receiver. In this view, a fascinating possibility is that also humanoid robots endowed with the capacity to generate VFs may induce the same effect on humans. Indeed, the opportunity of humanoid robots to

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EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS AND PARADIGM

FIGURE 1. Experimental setup of the video (A) and live (B) sessions. Experimental paradigm (C). **Target (1s):** instruction of the color target in which participants have to position the ball. **Request (1s):** participants are presented with the request of the iCub robot. **Action (3s):** participants reach the ball and move it on the correct target. **Reposition (5s):** instruction during which participants reposition the ball in the initial placement.

express different VFs would allow an immediate understanding of their intentions, making the interaction with human partners more comfortable and effective. Research in robotics has often focused on generation of human-like movements in the attempt of creating communicative actions [5], [6], [7], [8]. For example, different authors proposed to generate humanoid motions on the basis of the Laban Movement Analysis that describes the emotional component of movement by using parameters such as velocity, curvature and acceleration [9], [10], [24]. Recently several researchers rely on generative models to endow robots' motion with human-like expressivity [25], [26], [27], demonstrating promising results. However, to date, robotics has neglected the communicative role of VFs during the execution of actions, since there are no studies addressing the issue of the generation of VFs in humanoids. The challenge we addressed in this work was to study the motor behavior of participants during two different interactive contexts (video and live) in which the iCub robot performed gentle and rude actions conveying positive or negative attitudes towards them. To address this issue, we performed a motion retargeting: we firstly recorded the human kinematic features characterizing a single gentle/rude action (taking request) with a motion tracking system and subsequently remapped them into the joint space of the iCub robot. Secondly, we carried out a kinematic experiment in order to study the impact of these robotic actions on humans. In particular, participants were required to pay attention to a taking request performed gently or rudely by the iCub robot and subsequently to reach and place the requested

object on a specific target. On the basis of our previous results, we hypothesized a modulation effect produced by the perception of different VFs (gentle/rude) generated by the iCub robot on kinematic parameters of the human partner's response. Additionally, on the basis of previous studies demonstrating that people had stronger behavioral and attitudinal responses to a physically present agent as opposed to a virtually present one [11], we hypothesized a stronger VFs effect during the live interaction with the iCub robot.

II. METHODS

A. PARTICIPANTS

The experiment was carried out on 20 healthy right-handed volunteers 12 females and 8 males (mean age = 27.15 years; SD = 5.75 years). All participants were native Italian speakers and had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and normal hearing. None reported neurological or cognitive disorders. The study received approval by the ethical committee of Liguria Region (n.222REG2015) and was carried out according to the principles expressed in the Declaration of Helsinki. The participants provided written informed consent.

B. TASK AND PROCEDURE

Participants sat comfortably in front of a table, on which they placed their right hand with the thumb and index finger in a starting position (pinching, see Figure 1A-B). The experiment consisted of two different sessions corresponding to two different interactive contexts: video and live. In both sessions, participants were required to pay attention to a taking request

FIGURE 2. Starting (A1) and ending (A2) positions of iCub visual request. Action velocity curves characterizing rude (red line) and gentle (blue line) visual requests (B). Voice wave amplitudes characterizing rude (red) and gentle (blue) vocal requests (C).

performed by the iCub robot and subsequently grasp a small ball and place it on a target (yellow or orange). In particular, during the taking request the iCub robot moved its right arm with the palm upward to indicate the object with two different VFs (gentle and rude). Specifically, while in the live context participants were required to really interact with the iCub robot (see Figure 1B), in the video context the iCub robot was presented by using video-clips (see Figure 1A). The video-clips shown during the video session were arranged to show the same size of the real iCub during the live interaction. As done in our previous work [4], in order to control whether the participants' motor response was merely due to an automatic motor imitation of the iCub's gesture in its taking request, we introduced a control condition based on a vocal modality. In this control condition, the iCub robot pronounced the Italian action verb "prendi" (English verb "take it") in a gentle or rude way. During the vocal request, the hand of the iCub robot was always in end position (see Figure 2 A2). After this vocal (taking) request, participants were required to perform the same task described above. Since the facial information is an attractive social cue, the face of the robot was always covered in order to allow participants to focus their attention on the taking request. Before the experiment, participants performed a training session (baseline condition) in which they familiarized with the task by simply grasping and placing the ball on the indicated target without any request performed by the iCub robot. During each experimental session (video, live), stimuli were presented in three blocks of 16 repetitions. Specifically, each block consisted of 4 conditions (gentle action, gentle voice, rude action, rude voice) presented 4 times per block in a randomized order. The sequence of stimuli was the same

for all participants. Each experimental trial started with an instruction concerning the color of the target (yellow or orange) given by a neutral robotic voice, followed by the iCub robot action (taking request). According to the request, participants grasped the ball with their right hand and placed it on the correct target. Subsequently, they were instructed by a neutral robotic voice to replace the ball in the starting point with their left hand (see Figure 1C). Half of the participants started the experiment with the live session followed by the video one, while the other half started with the video session followed by the live one. The two sessions were performed in separate days.

C. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE STIMULI

1) VISUAL REQUEST

In order to generate a human-like movement for the iCub robot conveying gentle and rude VFs, we used a procedure previously adopted by Di Cesare et al. [12]. Specifically, we firstly recorded the kinematic data of a trained actor performing a taking request gently or rudely towards an object (indicate the object). We chose an actor whose anthropometric measures were similar to those of the iCub robot to ensure a higher compatibility between the robotic and the human stimuli. The kinematic features of the actor's actions were recorded by using the motion capture system NDI OptoTrack and remapped into the joint space of the iCub robot. This procedure allowed us to obtain an exact replica of the human action allowing the iCub robot to perform the same taking request with different VFs (gentle and rude). Each taking request always started from the same initial position (see Figure 2A1) and finished in the same ending position (see Figure 2A2). The velocity curves of rude and gentle requests are shown in Figure 2B.

2) VOCAL REQUEST

In order to generate a robotic voice, we used a procedure previously adopted by Vannucci et al. [13]. Specifically, we firstly recorded the voice of a human actor that pronounced the Italian motor command "prendi" (English verb "take it") gently and rudely. The vocal requests were recorded by using a cardioid condenser microphone (RODE NT1) placed 20 cm from the speaker and digitized with an A/D converter module with a phantom power supply (M-AUDIO M-TRACK). Secondly, the human voice was manipulated by using a sound effect (echo effect) implemented with the Cool Edit Pro Software. This procedure allowed us to generate two robotic vocal requests conveying two different VFs (gentle/rude). Subsequently, the physical characteristics of the vocal requests were analyzed by using MATLAB (The MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA) (see Figure 2C).

D. DATA RECORDING

Kinematic data were acquired by using an Optotrak tracking system (NDI) with active infrared markers (sampling

rate 100 Hz) placed on the right hand of each participant. From a marker at the center of the back of the hand, we extracted the speed and acceleration of hand motion during the reaching phase. Particularly, we measured the reach peak velocity and reach peak acceleration characterizing participants' motor responses after iCub's requests. The selection of these specific parameters was in accordance with those which mostly distinguish the rude and gentle actions performed by the iCub robot. Additional markers were used as a backup for reconstruction of the possible gaps in the motion tracking recordings. The kinematic data were analyzed by using MATLAB (R2020b).

E. RESULTS

To evaluate the effect of the iCub robot request (visual, vocal) on the participants' motor behavior, we measured possible differences of kinematic parameters (reach peak velocity and reach peak acceleration) characterizing the action response of participants. Before the analysis, data were normalized to the baseline condition (e.g., for the Rude condition, $\text{VIDEO_RD Velocity Peak (\%)} = (\text{VIDEO_RD Velocity Peak} * 100) / (\text{Velocity Peak Baseline})$) obtaining percentage values as shown in Figure 3A1. The experimental design comprised two factors: VITALITY (gentle and rude) and CONTEXT (video and live). Figure 3 reports the overall results of the analysis of participants' velocity peaks (A1-3) and acceleration peaks (B1-3). In particular, the different plots report the average and standard error of each variable across the sample for both VFs and both the video and the live context. Already from visual inspection it emerges a clear modulation of both kinematics parameters due to the style of the robotic action, which appears to be larger in the video-based context. The statistical analysis confirms these observations. Concerning the visual request, data were organized to carry out two different General Linear Models (GLMs). The first GLM comprised the velocity peaks of participants' responses after gentle and rude taking requests in both video (VEL_VIDEO_GT for Gentle; VEL_VIDEO_RD for Rude) and live (VEL_LIVE_GT; VEL_LIVE_RD) sessions. Results of this first GLM analysis indicated a significant principal effect of VITALITY ($F(1,19) = 42.23$, $p > 0.0001$), an effect close to significance of CONTEXT ($F(1,19) = 2.77$, $p = 0.1$) and a significant interaction effect VITALITY*CONTEXT ($F(1,19) = 41.45$, $p > 0.0001$). Post-hoc analysis (Newman-Keuls correction) revealed a significant difference among all conditions ($p > 0.0001$) except for the comparison VEL_VIDEO_GT vs VEL_LIVE_GT ($p = 0.39$) (see Figure 3A1). The second GLM comprised the acceleration peaks of participants' responses after gentle and rude taking requests in both video (ACC_VIDEO_GT; ACC_VIDEO_RD) and live (ACC_LIVE_GT; ACC_LIVE_RD) sessions. Results of this second GLM analysis indicated a significant principal effect of VITALITY ($F(1,19) = 29.45$, $p > 0.0001$), an effect close to significance of CONTEXT ($F(1,19) = 3.10$, $p = 0.09$) and a significant interaction effect VITALITY*CONTEXT

($F(1,19) = 55.04$, $p > 0.0001$). Post-hoc analysis (Newman-Keuls correction) revealed a significant difference among all conditions ($p > 0.0001$) except for the comparison ACC_VIDEO_GT vs ACC_LIVE_GT ($p = 0.15$) (see Figure 3A2). Figure 3 A2 depicts mean velocity curves relative to participants' action in response to gentle and rude visual requests, while Figure 3 B2 depicts mean acceleration curves relative to participants' action in response to the same requests. Finally, we quantified and compared the VFs effect (Δ VFs) of video and live interactions. Specifically, we subtracted the value of each kinematic parameter (velocity and acceleration peaks) after rude and gentle requests within each context (Δ VFs_VIDEO = VIDEO_RD-VIDEO_GT; VFs_LIVE = LIVE_RD-LIVE_GT) and then we compared them (paired t-test). Results indicated a significant difference in the modulation effect of VFs between video and live contexts ($p > 0.0001$, see Figure 3 A3-B3).

Concerning the vocal request (control condition), data were organized to carry out two different General Linear Models (GLMs). The first GLM comprised the velocity peaks of participants' responses after gentle and rude vocal requests in both video (VEL_VIDEO_GT; VEL_VIDEO_RD) and live (VEL_LIVE_GT; VEL_LIVE_RD) sessions. Results of the first GLM analysis indicated a significant principal effect of VITALITY ($F(1,19) = 8.33$, $p > 0.05$; for details see supplementary Figure S1 A1). No significant interaction was found between VITALITY*CONTEXT. The second GLM comprised the acceleration peaks of participants' responses after gentle and rude vocal requests in both video (ACC_VIDEO_GT; ACC_VIDEO_RD) and live (ACC_LIVE_GT; ACC_LIVE_RD) sessions. Results of the second GLM analysis only indicated an effect close to significance of VITALITY ($F(1,19) = 3.90$, $p = 0.06$; for details see supplementary Figure S1 A2).

III. DISCUSSION

Previous studies demonstrated that, during social interactions, kinematic parameters of human actions are affected by positive/negative attitudes expressed by others. Particularly, Di Cesare et al. showed that a rude request ("give me") induced a motor response characterized by higher velocity and larger trajectory [3]. In contrast, the same request expressed in a gentle way produced a motor response with lower velocity and smaller trajectory. These findings are corroborated by Lombardi et al. showing that when participants received a gentle/rude physical request mediated by a robotic manipulandum, their action execution and action planning (motor imagery of the action) were influenced by the perceived VFs [4]. Taken together, these findings indicate the existence of a contagion effect produced by VFs during human-human and human-robot interactions. An intriguing issue concerns the possibility to investigate whether and how a humanoid agent able to generate VFs may induce the same contagion effect on humans. For this purpose, we firstly attempted to endow the iCub robot with the capacity to convey two different VFs by replicating a human action (taking

FIGURE 3. Mean velocity (A1) and acceleration (B1) peaks normalized to the baseline condition (dotted line at 100%) characterizing participants' response after rude (red color) and gentle (blue color) visual requests. Vertical bars represent the standard errors (SE). Horizontal bars indicate statistical significance (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$). Mean velocity (A2) and acceleration (B2) curves of participants' response after rude (red line) and gentle (blue line) visual requests. Error shadings indicate standard error of the mean. VFs effect comparison (paired t-test, *** $p < 0.001$) between video (green color) and live (yellow color) contexts (A3-B3).

request) performed gently or rudely. Secondly, we studied the motor behavior of participants in response to these actions performed by the iCub robot in video and live interactive contexts. Results showed that, for both video and live contexts, participants performed the task significantly faster exhibiting higher acceleration when they observed a rude robotic action request. In contrast, they became slower and more relaxed when they observed a gentle robotic action request. Notably, the same influence of VFs on participants' motor response was also found when the same request was expressed vocally by the iCub robot (control condition), remarking that this contagion effect was present regardless to the modality (visual,

vocal). Furthermore, the presence of a VFs effect obtained with a vocal request highlights that the contagion was not merely due to a motor imitation of the observed action. These results are completely in line with previous works [3], [4], [23] suggesting that the effect of VFs is independent of the modality (visual, auditory, tactile) or the agent (male, female, humanoid) with which they are conveyed. A key point of our work was the investigation of the role of VFs in human-robot interaction in two different contexts: video and live. Notably, the iCub robot represented an ideal interactive agent, since it is a fully controllable platform which provided the repeatability necessary to perform always the same identical requests

during the live interaction with participants. Based on previous results demonstrating that robots led to better user performance when they were physically present as opposed to shown via video on a screen [11], we expected a stronger effect of VFs on participants' motor response during the live interaction compared to the video one. Results showed that the modulation effect of VFs on participants' motor response was considerably greater in the video interactive context (when iCub requests was presented by video) compared to the live interactive context (when iCub was physically present in front of them). To explain these findings, we hypothesized that an inhibition mechanism occurred during the live interaction. Indeed, it is reasonable to assume that participants may have controlled their automatic reactions in presence of an agent that, by communicating a specific attitude, could physically impact them and put them at risk. Moreover, a stronger sensation of participants to be seen by the iCub robot when present in front of them could represent another possible explanation of a weaker VFs effect during the live interaction. This hypothesis is line with a recent study showing that the experience of being seen during a live interaction is essential for an increased autonomic reaction [14], [15]. It is important to note that, although the different magnitude of VFs effect between the two interactive contexts (video and live), the contagion produced by VFs occurred in both of them. A plausible explanation of this phenomenon regards the capability of the iCub robot to replicate human VFs. Indeed, for the first time, the humanoid robot was able to perform the same human actions with the same kinematic features. This idea was confirmed by a recent functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) study demonstrating that only the observation of iCub actions performed with human VFs elicited a BOLD signal increase in the left dorso-central insula, a key region selectively involved during VFs processing. In contrast, the observation of iCub performing the same action simply with two different peak velocities (a fast and a slow movement), and not replicating the detailed kinematic properties of the VFs did not activate the insula [12]. This reveals that some kinematic features of human behavior (such as acceleration) are fundamental in conveying different VFs and consequently activating the dorso-central insula. Recently, Di Cesare et al. showed that the dorso-central insula and middle cingulate cortex constitute a circuit not only involved during the perception of VFs, but also during their execution [16]. In this view, it is plausible to hypothesize that, during the observation of actions, this circuit may encode and integrate some features characterizing action VFs and use this information to prepare an appropriate motor response during the execution of actions. The activation of the same circuit during the observation and execution of VFs represents the possible explanation for the contagion effect obtained in our experiment. Indeed, this mechanism could allow the observer to understand the affective component of the agent's action and to automatically adapt their motor behavior, promoting a continuous and reciprocal interaction. The implementation of the iCub robot able to replicate human VFs modulating

the motor response of participants represents a crucial point not only for neuroscience but also for robotics. Indeed, VFs could be a valuable property for future robots allowing them to assume the right attitude in different scenarios, such as an authoritative role in the security contexts or a polite behavior in clinical ones, influencing some social cues such as trust [17], empathy [18], and attachment [19].

IV. CONCLUSION AND LIMITATIONS

In the present study, our main goals were twofold: investigating the effect of VFs expressed by the iCub robot on participants' motor behavior and understanding if this contagion effect occurs in two different interactive contexts (video and live). There are three main results. First, VFs conveyed by the iCub robot influenced the motor response of participants regardless the modality (visual, vocal). Second, this effect was obtained for both video and live interactive contexts. Finally, the modulation effect observed during the interaction with the iCub robot was significantly greater in the video session compared to the live one. A first limitation may be related to the vocal stimuli adopted in the control condition. Particularly, the echo effect used to create the robotic voice may have mitigated differences between gentle and rude vocal requests, reducing their effect on the response of participants. In future studies, the audio stimuli conveying VFs could be improved by replicating the same physical properties characterizing human gentle/rude voices. A second limitation may be related to the interaction between the iCub robot and participants. Indeed, both video and live interactions consisted always of the same taking requests presented in the same randomized order for each participant. Moreover, participants were always asked to perform a motor response after the iCub robot request. In this view, the modulation effect of VFs on human motor behavior should be investigated in more natural, dynamic and ecological interactive contexts. Additionally, future experiments could study the same VFs effect with different robotic embodiments or with a robot in presence (live interaction) but separated from participants with a transparent barrier (in order to exclude the participant's fear of a potential collision). Finally, it is important to consider that our study was performed in an Italian context and Italians frequently communicate using body language e.g. talking "with their hands". This could have enhanced the effect of VFs on participants. In the future, it would be interesting to carry out the same study in other geo-cultural contexts where VFs might be expressed and perceived differently. To conclude, the present study showed that a humanoid robot expressing different VFs influenced and modulated the human motor behavior in two different interactive contexts. In this view, it is plausible that, in future, VFs could become an essential feature of humanoid robots, enabling them to communicate different attitudes in several scenarios [20], [21], [22].

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(Fabio Vannucci, Giada Lombardi, and Giuseppe Di Cesare contributed equally to this work.)

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